

Deliverable 2.2

CPS Community Roadmap Report

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List of Abbreviations

5G	Fifth Generation of cellular mobile communications
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CC	Competence Centre
Cobot	Collaborative Robot
COTS	Commercial Off-The-Shelf
CPS	Cyber-Physical System
CPSoS	Cyber-Physical System of Systems
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DEI	Digitising European Industry
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
DSM	Digital Single Market
EC	European Commission
ECS	Embedded Component and Systems
ECSEL	Electronic Components and Systems for European Leadership
FoF	Factory of the Future
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HMI	Human-Machine Interaction
I4MS	ICT Innovation for Manufacturing SMEs
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IIoT	Industrial Internet of Things
IoT	Internet of Things
JU	Joint Undertaking
NGI	Next Generation Internet
NOE	Network of Excellence
NRMES	National Roadmap Embedded Systems
OBD	On Board Diagnostic
PPP	Public Private Partnership
PSI	Public Sector Information
R&I	Research and Innovation
SAE	Smart Anything Everywhere
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
SoS	System of Systems
SRA	Strategic Research Agenda
STEM (skills)	Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics
V&V	Verification and Validation

1 Executive Summary

The Platforms4CPS '**CPS Community Roadmap Report**' summarises the findings of the projects comparative roadmap analysis and complementing 'Roadmap Consensus Workshops', deriving a common view on future research priorities, barriers and enablers as well as recommendations for CPS related development and deployment activities. The aim of the document is to give an overview on the results and perspectives of recent and ongoing CPS-related roadmaps, analyse converging visions and to obtain consensus between main stakeholders in terms of required future actions across Europe.

Various roadmaps, vision and strategy documents have been analysed in the field of **Digitising the European Industry** mainly in Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS), Cyber-Physical System of Systems (CPSoS), Embedded Components and Systems (ECS), Advanced Computing, and Factories of the Future (FoF). Moreover, the respective representatives of these documents were involved in different workshops to discuss visions and priorities and draw **recommendations for future research and innovation**.

Amongst the **technological topics**, and related future **research priorities**, integration, interoperability and standards ranked very highly. A topic connected to digital platforms and reference architectures, which have already become a key priority theme for the EC and their Digitisation Strategy. Another theme of very high relevance revealed to be autonomous CPS in connection with robotics and edge computing. This also features strongly in the EC 2030 vision for the upcoming Horizon Europe Framework Program. Important underlying technological themes are situational awareness, improved forecasting, decision-making, Artificial Intelligence and learning. Key to the future will be safety and security of such systems. This engenders trust, which will be crucial to the uptake of new autonomous technologies. The human-in-the-loop was also identified as being a key future challenge that will need to be solved by new CPS engineering approaches suitable for the ever-growing complexity in evolving systems.

In summary, **consensus research priority themes** across various roadmaps included:

- Data analytics and (collaborative) **decision support**
- **Trustable AI-enabled autonomous CPS**, cognitive systems and situation awareness
- **Human in the loop**, HMI, intuitive systems, wearables, virtual and augmented reality
- CPS (virtual) **engineering** of large, complex systems including modelling & simulation
- CPS **reference architectures** and standards
- Agile, open, vertical and horizontal, federated, (dynamic) plug-and-play **CPS platforms**
- **Integration**, (semantic) interoperability, flexibility, composability and reconfiguration
- Seamless **connectivity**, edge **computing**, intelligent edge devices, energy efficiency
- **Safety**, reliability & (cyber)**security, privacy and trust**

Main barriers to overcome are difficulties regarding the integration of legacy systems, missing interoperability and standards, the fragmentation of initiatives and across application domains and missing skills (knowledge, competences, IT-education, interdisciplinarity). Mastering complexity, terminology, semantics and overcoming concerns regarding safety and stability will be crucial for the success of future CPSs. A major hurdle, next to high implementation costs and missing demonstration, are concerns regarding security, privacy and confidentiality of such systems. Business related barriers include missing business models, missing openness (open data) and fear of vendor lock. Supporting legal frameworks, regulation, certification, IPR protection, liability, are also not yet in place. Conservatism, resistance to change and missing entrepreneurial thinking are additional barriers. Access to technologies and infrastructures is seen as difficult, especially for SMEs and start-ups.

Critically, user acceptance and trust need to be ensured and ethical concerns overcome. Without a deep and critical dialogue, positive vision and mindful path to implement such pervasive and partially autonomous systems, societal concerns might become the main showstopper to CPS deployment.

Innovation accelerators, needed for successful implementation were particularly pointed out to be multi-disciplinarity and cross-fertilising approaches as well as coordinated collaboration to reduce fragmentation across the EU. Education (T-shape, lifelong learning and reskilling) and CPS enabled business models and services were seen as very important. Demonstrators and living lab are considered as essential to alleviate concerns and regulatory, legal and ethical issues to ensure a reliable framework. Not only societal dialogue and awareness raising but also real user acceptance and trust appeared as crucial elements of future CPS success. Further points included to focus EC incentives on open source solutions and open approaches related to data, platform building and innovations.

In summary, important **priorities to support successful CPS implementation** were highlighted to be:

- **Collaboration** across initiatives, engineering / application domains, international collaboration
- Access of **SMEs, start-ups and scale-ups** to the ecosystem
- **Openness**, open data, open innovation and open platforms
- Demonstration, **pilot lines** and living labs
- CPS enabled **business models** and business services
- CPS standardisation, **regulation**, liability, **privacy** and **ethics**
- T-shape, cross-disciplinary **education**, lifelong learning and (re/up)skilling
- Raise **awareness**, promote societal dialogue, enhance user acceptance and trust
- Create a **positive vision** and respective plan for CPS developments and implementation

Regarding the **technology trends** and new/**emerging themes**, 'autonomous systems' became very prominent in connection with 'Artificial Intelligence' and 'trust'. New or improved (virtual) CPS engineering approaches to manage the more and more complex systems including the human as a part of the system, but also co-engineered safety and security as a part of it were discussed intensively. Agile (open source) platforms as well as the federation of platforms also ranged high amongst the future challenges. In terms of **societal and economic trends** IT-systems tend to become 'addictive', with an enhanced dependence of society on these, but at the same time an increasing vulnerability. A positive vision of the 'digitised new world' to follow is still missing. Openness, open data and open innovation became more prominent topics over the last years. Business models become more decoupled from ownership, and topics like servitisation, data driven economy, crowd funding, blockchain are arising. T-shape (broad and deep) education and lifelong learning is crucial for competitiveness and will become a focus also to avoid the digital divide.

Platforms4CPS recommends that Europe should enhance activities to master 'trustworthy CPS for AI (artificial intelligence) enabled autonomous systems with humans in the loop', exploit 'CPS edge computing' and 'co-engineering of CPS system attributes' and provide 'trust' as well as maintaining sovereignty in key value chains. Platforms4CPS emphasises, that research activities have to be embedded into a suitable innovation environment and answering real societal needs.

The Platforms4CPS community recommendations target to catalyse progress in key technological and non-tech fields, following a cross-disciplinary, multi-domain and inclusive approach, and to build and bond an ecosystem bringing relevant stakeholders together to **speak with one voice**.

2 Introduction and Context – European Digitisation Strategy

Digital transformation and mainstreaming digital innovations across all sectors is now considered a necessity in order to stay ahead in the race for global advantage. Digital is in fact a driver for economic growth, as stated in the European Commission’s Communication on Digitising European Industry (COM (2016)180 final): ‘Embracing digital technologies will help companies to grow beyond the EU internal market and make the EU an even more attractive location for global investments’ [23].

To reinforce the EU's competitiveness in digital technologies and to ensure that every industry in Europe, in whichever sector, wherever situated, and no matter of what size can fully benefit from digital innovations, the European Commission launched Digitising European Industry (DEI) initiative [23] in April 2016. It is the first industry-focused initiative of the Digital Single Market and it is a unique opportunity for companies to modernise, integrate digital cross-sectorial innovations and become leaders in the next generation of products, services, processes and business models.

The initiative is framed into the following lines of actions with a clear European added value:

- **European platform of national initiatives on digitising industry:** EU coordination forum bringing together all Member States to ensure coherence and a collective approach.
- **Digital innovations for all - Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs):** DIHs are networked one-stop-shops to help businesses to ensure they can take advantage of digital opportunities.
- **Strengthening leadership through partnerships and industrial platforms:** Support the development of digital industrial platforms and large-scale piloting to provide the digital technology building blocks of the future.
- **A regulatory framework fit for the digital age:** Create a digital-friendly regulatory framework.
- **Preparing Europeans for the digital future:** Ensure that all Europeans are ready for the digital transformation by adapting the workforce, education systems and reskill citizens.

Figure 1. Activities to support the Digitisation of European Industry under Horizon 2020 (Source: EC)

Considering **Cyber-Physical Systems**, the elements of the “Digitising European Industry” initiative are all of great importance: i) creation of a pan-European network of Digital Innovation Hubs supporting businesses with CPS technologies ii) synchronisation of national initiatives, iii) support of digital CPS platforms and standards, and finally iv) putting in place a supporting regulatory framework and skills.

3 Cyber-Physical Systems

The goal of a Cyber-Physical System (CPS) is to enable cyber-space to physically interact with the real world. They are hardware-software systems, which tightly couple the physical and the virtual world. CPS are everywhere around us in transportation systems, industrial production systems, energy systems, and robotics for health care. CPS network together embedded systems that are connected to the physical world through sensors and actuators and have the capability to collaborate, adapt, and evolve. An increasing number of systems are being interconnected on a more global scale via the Internet of Things (IoT). Although IoT research and development has been focused on wireless sensors and on providing connectivity in the past, there is now more emphasis on “closing the loop” to use the information provided by the sensors and networks in a smart way to provide actuation to bring value to the users and to society such as reducing emissions, improving energy and resource efficiency, and providing better services at a lower cost and in a sustainable manner. Thus, while CPS and IoT strengths lie in active and passive systems respectively, there is significant benefit from technology exchanges between them.

Figure 2. Some definitions of Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS)

There are a number of different definitions for CPS as shown in Figure 1 ^{[1] [5] [15] [22]} but they all are underpinned via a common understanding of the need to integrate sensing, computation, networking and actuation in order to perform some physical action. There is an increasing number of interacting systems with strong connectivity utilised in both society and in industry with applications in multi-modal transport, eHealth, smart factories, smart grids and smart cities among others. Enhanced by the advancements in various related technologies (Cloud Computing, Big Data Analytics, etc.), the deployment of CPS is expected to increase substantially over the next decades, providing great potential for novel applications and innovative product development. Many new and exciting markets are predicted and here it is important to look at both the opportunities and the barriers.

However, the inherent complexity of CPSs, as well as the need to meet optimised performance and comply with essential requirements like safety, security and privacy, raises many questions that still need to be explored by the research community. This requires strategic investment, as well as development of supporting standards and regulation.

4 Approach and Methodology

The Platforms4CPS project is a 24-months coordination and support action (November 2016 – October 2018), co-funded under the European Union's H2020 Research and Innovation Program in the area of Smart Cyber-Physical Systems. Taking up the results of its precursor Road2CPS, the project aims to carry out strategic action for future CPS through roadmaps, support of platform development and constituency building. Platforms4CPS is coordinated by Thales and supported by six other partners (Steinbeis2i, THINK, Festo, KTH, fortiss and Systematic) from 4 European countries (France, Germany, UK and Sweden) pursuing the following objectives:

- Create a vision and strategy for future European CPS by analysing the ecosystem and market and strategically updating and validating existing CPS roadmaps across multiple domains
- Promote platform building, bringing together industry and academic experts and create a repository of CPS technology building blocks
- Build an ecosystem, cooperate on the foundations of CPS engineering, and build consensus on societal and legal issues related to the deployment of CPS

Figure 3. Overview on the Platforms4CPS approach

The document at hand summarises the findings from the Roadmapping activities, building on outputs from the other pillars and community inputs.

The primary objective of the Platforms4CPS Roadmapping activities is to strategically update, validate and harmonise the many CPS roadmaps that already exist. To gain a complete picture, Platforms4CPS mapped existing CPS roadmaps and then held a series of three Roadmap Consensus Workshops. These workshops brought key stakeholders from industry, academia and policy-making together, to discuss and define research priorities, enablers and barriers for successful implementation as well as innovation strategies to enhance CPS deployment. The results, together with other inputs from the project activities, were compiled and analysed to derive this **CPS Community Roadmap Report**.

Following this aim, activities focussed on:

- Mapping the national, European and international CPS/IoT roadmap landscape
- Identifying and discussing CPS concepts, research challenges, enabling technologies and barriers
- Holding a series of ‘Roadmap Consensus Workshops’, with representatives of recent and ongoing CPS related roadmaps as well as relevant stakeholders from academia, industry and policy making
- Evaluating research priorities, approaches to addressing the major enablers and barriers for successful CPS deployment, and defining implementation strategies
- Creating the Community Roadmap including a ‘Research and Technology Radar’
- Supporting the CPS community consensus building process by encompassing the views and initiating a discussion amongst key stakeholders as well as the development of the ecosystem

The community-driven activity has benefitted considerably from past and ongoing roadmapping activities by the partners of the consortium, but also the valuable contributions from other roadmap representatives and CPS experts in workshops and interviews.

In addition to the community inputs, the Platforms4CPS project builds on the results of further project inputs, applying a combination of the technology-push and market-pull approach:

- A technology-driven approach identifies new research results (incl. foundations, concepts, methods, platforms/architectures, tools) and research fields with a high potential for a technological breakthrough, resulting in recommendations for future research priorities.
- A market-driven approach identifies trends, socio-economical needs, barriers as well as future applications and business opportunities.
- The CPS Community Roadmap combines the technology-push and market-pull perspectives.

Figure 4. Overview on the Platforms4CPS roadmapping methodology

The CPS Community Roadmap emerged from the integration and combination of these routes and is further analysed towards extracting information to derive recommendations for future research priorities and innovation strategies (Deliverable D2.3). The document at hand has the aim to inform industry, academia and policy-making on the latest up-to-date findings of different roadmaps, but to also give an overall picture on similarities and differences found through the different perspectives presented. It also serves as the knowledge base to derive recommendations targeted at the European Commission regarding future research programs.

5 Analysis of CPS Roadmaps

Strategic documents such as roadmaps, visions and research agendas (to advise the European Commission on future research priorities and implementation strategies) are often elaborated by European Technology Platforms, related Associations or Public-Private-Partnerships (PPPs). In the field of Embedded and Cyber-Physical Systems, the ARTEMIS European Technology Platform turned into the **ARTEMIS Industry Association** (Advanced Research and Technology for Embedded Intelligence and Systems) being responsible for the ARTEMIS Strategic Research Agenda (SRA). The **ARTEMIS-SRA** (from 2006 to 2016) was not only the basis for ARTEMIS specific calls, but also the strategic grounds for the other H2020 (ICT-1 Smart Cyber-Physical-Systems) topics to be funded. Together with **ITEA**, the ARTEMIS-IA published a high-level vision 2013.

The **ECSEL-JU** (Electronic Components and Systems for European Leadership) program was created from a merger of ARTEMIS-JU and the ENIAC-JU in June 2014 and will finish in 2024. ECSEL has coverage from industry in a number of areas including micro-/nanoelectronics, embedded and Cyber-Physical Systems and smart systems. The strategy of ECSEL is decided by a Governing Board, which comprises the ARTEMIS-IA, AENEAS and EPoSS, participating states and the European Commission. ECSEL makes its own calls to fund R&I projects via the Public Authorities Board. Call topics are based on the **ECSEL-MASRIA/MASP** and agreed by participating states, associated countries and the European Commission. The MASRIA contained a fusion of the three Roadmaps of the individual members. This process has been changed during 2017 and a new ECS-SRA (Electronic Components and Systems - Strategic Research Agenda) was issued, without developing individual roadmaps beforehand.

Figure 5. The MASP elaboration process (left) and ECS-SRA possible impact on various programs (right)

Next to these funding relevant strategic research agendas, CPS-related roadmaps, visions and theme specific research agendas have also been funded by the EU under FP7 (Road2SoS, CyPhERS, CPSoS) and H2020 (Road2CPS, TAMS4CPS, CPSSummit, HiPEAC, Platforms4CPS) in the ICT-1 program. They typically have a budget of 1-2 MEuro, a duration of 2 years and are more focussed regarding the themes. They partly feed into the above mentioned strategic research agendas.

Figure 6. Overview on EC funded CPS Roadmaps, Visions and Research Agendas under FP7 and H2020 within the ICT-Programme

Historically, the European CPS roadmaps are closely related to two German national roadmaps (NMRS, National Roadmap for Embedded Systems and AgendaCPS) [3] [34]. In addition, European Strategic roadmaps have been put forward by Industry, e.g. the ECSEL Strategic Research Agenda [18], ARTEMIS-IA [5] [6] [7] [8], EFFRA [14] [30] Electronics Industry [33] and a number of CPS-related roadmaps, visions and theme specific research agendas have also been funded by the EU under FP7 (Road2SoS [4] [47], CyPhERS [10] [49], CPSoS [19], Road4FAME [9] [48]) and H2020 (Road2CPS [45] [46], TAMS4CPS [35], CPSSummit [11], HiPEAC [13] [15] [16], PICASSO [50], Platforms4CPS [41] [42] [43] [44], MANUFUTURE [31], sCorPiuS [52]) in the ICT-1 program. The chronology for these roadmaps is given in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Timeline for roadmaps

5.1 Comparison of individual Roadmaps

The following chapter summarises the outcomes of different CPS roadmaps regarding research priorities, barriers and enablers as well as strategic recommendations in CPS (and related fields).

5.1.1 National Roadmap Embedded Systems - NRMES (2009)

The NRMES was published in 2009 in German on behalf of the BMBF (Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung – German Ministry for Education and Research) with the contribution of 40 partners from industry and research. The NRMES had already introduced the notion of Embedded Systems/Cyber-Physical Systems being ‘the central nervous system of society’. It provides a detailed analysis of the needs and requirements for R&D&I, including public funding and support as well as a ‘Technology Radar’ (which served as an inspiration for the Platforms4CPS Research and Technology Radar). The Roadmap has influenced national and European funding programs and is still used as input and reference in today’s roadmaps.

The following picture shows the main themes and evolution of sub-themes as envisaged in 2009.

Figure 8. NRMES roadmap ‘technology radar’ (2009)

Link to the NRMES roadmap: http://netzwerk-zukunft-industrie.de/wp-content/uploads/2016/01/Anlage-3_Nationale-Roadmap-Embedded-Systems.pdf

5.1.2 AgendaCPS (2012)

The agendaCPS was published in 2012 in German on behalf of the National Academy of Science and Engineering, coordinated by Manfred Broy. With this agenda, the term CPS was introduced in Europe. The broad and thorough evaluation of societal and technical aspects of CPS became, amongst others the basis for the Industry 4.0 programme. The agendaCPS was translated into English in the course of the CyPhERS project (published 2015).

The following table presents a selection of research priorities, barriers and enablers, implementation priorities and strategic recommendations.

Research priorities	Barriers/enablers	Priorities for implementation	Strategic recommendations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concepts for platforms for development and operation • Development methods, processes and tools incl. V&V for complex, autonomous, cooperating CPS • Human machine interaction and human factors (customer centric development processes) • Safety, security, reliability, for complex, autonomous, cooperating CPS • Interdisciplinary modelling of hybrid systems • Model based development processes • Virtual engineering (cross-engineering-domain, cross-application-domain), incl. seamless, interoperable engineering/development tool-chains 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User acceptance and trust • Lack of business models • Lack of interoperability standards • Lack of available infrastructure and platforms for development and operation • Lack of cross-engineering-domain and cross-application-domain knowledge and methods 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enable user-acceptance and trust <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Support R&D&I in human-machine interaction and cooperation, safety, security, reliability, etc. • Support standardisation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - interoperability (run-time, semantic interoperability) - interoperability (design-time) • Education <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - on CPS usage - interdisciplinary CPS development 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Align infrastructure and economic structure to CPS requirements <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide mobile internet access and intelligent communication infrastructure - Support/create development platforms and operator platforms • Initiate public discourse <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Involve general public in the ,how and why‘ of CPS development and usage - Transparency of safety, security, reliability issues - Include politics and lawyers • Support SMEs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Easy access to projects - Cooperation platforms and networks - Special support for start-ups • Create legal framework for operating CPS

Table 1: agendaCPS – selection of CPS research priorities, barriers and recommendations

Link to roadmap agendaCPS (English / German):

http://www.cyphers.eu/sites/default/files/acatech_STUDIE_agendaCPS_eng_ANSICHT.pdf

https://www.bmbf.de/files/acatech_STUDIE_agendaCPS_Web_20120312_superfinal.pdf

The Platforms4CPS Consensus Workshop presentation is available under the following link:

https://www.platforms4cps.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/06_NRMES_SafeTrans_RoadmapPitch.pdf

5.1.3 Road2SoS (2014)

Road2SoS (Development of strategic research and engineering roadmaps in Systems of Systems (SoS) Engineering and related case studies; October 2011 - January 2014) was a coordination and support action co-financed by the European Commission under the FP7 ICT Work Programme. The aim of the project was the development of research and engineering roadmaps, which identify future RTD and innovation strategies for Europe in the field of SoS engineering in four domains. The goal of the roadmaps were: help to adapt SoS approaches; identify domain-specific drivers, barriers, scenarios; identify cross-domain commonalities in SoS; provide recommendations for research priorities.

The following table presents a selection of research priorities, barriers and enablers, implementation priorities and strategic recommendations.

Research priorities	Barriers/enablers	Priorities for implementation	Strategic recommendations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visualisation, virtualisation, situational awareness & decision support • Architectural patterns, decision structures and system architectures • Distributed, reliable and efficient mgt of CPS / SoS • Modelling & simulation • Understanding emergence • Engineering for resilience, adaptability and flexibility • Human machine interfaces 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interoperability, integration of legacy systems • Safety and reliability of evolving systems • Security, privacy, trust • Resistance to change • Costs, unclear return of investment • Missing regulatory framework (IP, multiple ownership) • Missing business models 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interoperability, standardisation, reference architectures and tools • Platforms (organisational, technological, operational, customer) • Security, privacy, trust & regulatory issues, IP • Demonstrations, living labs • Business models 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open platforms, reference architectures & tools • Fund demonstration • Facilitate funding to SMEs • Fund CSAs / task forces on business models, standardisation • Raise awareness & education, de-fragmentation & cross-fertilisation

Table 2: Road2CPS – selection of CPS research priorities, barriers and recommendations

Figure 9. Road2CPS research priorities

Link to the project website: <http://road2sos-project.eu>

More information on the project outcomes can be found in the Road2SoS Ebook: https://www.steinbeis-europa.de/files/road2sos_2015_ebook.pdf

5.1.4 CyPhERS Roadmap (2015)

The CyPhERS roadmap (Cyber-Physical European Roadmap and Strategy; July 2013 - February 2015) had the aim to develop an integrated strategic CPS research agenda for Europe and derive comprehensive recommendations for action that cover the identification and prioritisation of research areas, support measures for both horizontal and vertical cooperation, possible research partnerships, and address questions of research funding as well as the issues of training, standardisation and policies. The roadmap derived the following recommendations for action:

- **Strengthen key research:** Intensify enabling sciences, address human-machine interaction, foster cross-disciplinary research
- **Accelerate maturation of technologies:** Support maturation initiatives, promote available infrastructure, coordinate installation of key systems
- **Facilitate interoperability of technology:** Provide reference platforms, homogenise interoperability standards, define system-level design methodologies
- **Support open innovation:** Provide open standards, promote open source and open license, increase open data
- **Anticipate new business models:** Activate networks for open innovation, facilitate business service infrastructure, provide clear liability frameworks
- **Foster enabling education and training:** Stimulate collaboration in education, promote lifelong learning, support T-shaped education, provide educational platforms
- **Raise societal awareness:** Enable decision makers, stimulate public discussion, achieve societal consensus
- **Ensure trustworthiness:** Harden infrastructure, protect data ownership, adapt dependability regulations

The following table presents a selection of research priorities, barriers and enablers, implementation priorities and strategic recommendations.

Research priorities	Barriers/enablers	Priorities for implementation	Strategic recommendations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enabling sciences • Cross-disciplinary research • Human machine interaction • Interoperability standards • System-level design • Reference platforms • Open source & license 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technological barriers: Complexity • Scientific barriers: Multi-paradigm • Education barriers: Competence • Economic barriers: Disruption • Innovation barriers: Legislation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Available infrastructure • Open standards • Open innovation • Service infrastructure • Education platforms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordinate installation of key systems • Increase open data • Provide clear liability Frameworks • Foster education and training • Raise societal awareness

Table 3: CyPhERS – selection of CPS research priorities, barriers and recommendations

Link to the project website: <http://www.cyphers.eu/project>

The Platforms4CPS Consensus Workshop presentation is available under the following link:

https://www.platforms4cps.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/02_Cyphers-Pitch_fortiss_RoadmapPitch.pdf

5.1.5 CPSoS Roadmap (2016)

CPSoS (Towards a European Roadmap on Research and Innovation in Engineering and Management of Cyber-physical Systems of Systems), was a 30 month support action (October 2013 - June 2016). The goal of the project was to define a European research and innovation agenda on CPSoS using a bottom-up and top-down approach by analysing the needs in application domains, analysing the state of the art in methods and tools, and integrating the two views to define the most important gaps and actions needed. The project identified the key R&I challenges to be:

Distributed management of Cyber-Physical Systems of Systems

- Decision structures and system architectures
- Self-organisation, structure formation, and emergent behaviour in technical SoS
- Real-time monitoring, exception handling, fault detection, mitigation of faults/degradation
- Adaptation and integration of new components
- Humans-in-the-loop and collaborative decision making
- Trust in large distributed systems

Engineering support for the design-operation continuum of Cyber-Physical Systems of Systems

- Support of the design-operation continuum of Cyber-Physical Systems of Systems
- Integrated engineering of CPSoS over their full life-cycle
- Establishing system-wide and key properties of CPSoS
- Modelling, simulation, and optimisation of CPSoS

Cognitive CPSoS

- Situational awareness in large distributed systems with decentralised management/control
- Handling large amounts of data in real time to monitor the system performance and to detect faults and degradation
- Learning good operation patterns from past examples, auto-reconfiguration and adaptation
- Analysis of user behaviour and detection of needs and anomalies

The following table presents a selection of research priorities, barriers and enablers, implementation priorities and strategic recommendations.

Research priorities	Barriers/enablers	Priorities for implementation	Strategic needs / recommendations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distributed management of CPSoS • Engineering support for the design-operation continuum of CPSoS • Cognitive CPSoS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legacy systems integration • Lack of interdisciplinary heterogeneous, multi-scale CPSoS modelling at different levels of resolution • Certification of safety-critical CPSoS (parts) • Integration, processing, and management of high-quality data across a complete CPSoS • Data sources are often not yet accessible to a degree that is needed for CPSoS services and applications • CPSoS require continuous monitoring based on high-quality data sets to detect malfunctions and abnormal operation • Cybersecurity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • System integration and reconfiguration • Resiliency in large systems • Distributed robust system-wide optimisation • Data based system operation • Predictive maintenance for improved asset management • Overcoming the modelling bottleneck • Humans in the loop 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Full-life-cycle engineering • Coordination and optimisation • Modelling, simulation, and model management • System-wide validation and verification • Systems integration • Humans in the loop

Table 4: CPSoS – selection of CPS research priorities, barriers and recommendations

Link to the project website: <http://www.cpsos.eu/> and brochure www.cpsos.eu/roadmap. The Platforms4CPS Consensus Workshop presentation is available under the following link: https://www.platforms4cps.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/03_CPSoS_THINK_RoadmapPitch.pdf

5.1.6 Road2CPS Roadmap (2017)

Road2CPS (Strategic action for future CPS through roadmaps, impact multiplication and constituency building; February 2015 - January 2017) was a coordination and support action co-financed by the EC in the H2020 ICT-1 (CPS) Work Programme. The aim of the project was the development of a research, application and strategy roadmap, to derive recommendations for future research programs. Next to this, the project did an impact analysis of past and ongoing CPS projects and enhanced community involvement through task force actions. The following table presents a selection of research priorities, barriers and enablers, implementation priorities and strategic recommendations.

Research priorities	Barriers/enablers	Priorities for implementation	Strategic recommendations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration, interoperability, standards, platforms, reference architectures • (cyber)security, privacy, confidentiality, trust • Autonomous systems, Cognitive systems, artificial intelligence • (Big) data real time analysis • CPS / virtual engineering / modelling and simulation • Safety, reliability, resilience, fault tolerance • Human machine awareness, HMI • CPS foundations / science 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concerns on safety, security and privacy • Lack of interoperability and standards • High implementation costs • Conservatism of decision makers • Social acceptance of pervasive IT systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education, training, skills and reskilling • Ecosystem, community building, networks, collaboration (regional, national, global / across domains, value chains / cross-disciplinary) • Demonstrators, living labs • Business models • Societal dialogue, Awareness raising • Openness: Open data, architectures, platforms, open innovation, open environments, open ecosystems • Regulation, legal issues, Single Digital Market • Ethics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Invest in research priorities • Fund platforms and reference architectures & tools (interoperability / standardisation) • Facilitate funding to SMEs & inclusion of start-ups • Support innovation take-up action & accelerate ecosystem development, de-fragmentation & cross-fertilisation • Fund demonstration, test beds, show cases, (large scale) pilots, living labs • Fund CSAs, NoE, CCs, DIHs, task forces, working groups • Raise awareness, promote societal dialogue • Invest in training and education

Table 5: Road2CPS – selection of CPS research priorities, barriers and recommendations

Next to this, recommendations included the ‘facilitation of business and ecosystems’

- Invest not only on the **supply side**, but on the **demand side**
- **Collaboration between all stakeholders** from the beginning for balanced decision-making
- **Citizen engagement** is needed as a result of the impact of new technologies (e.g. wearables) where privacy could be breached
- **Don’t over-regulate** and adapt to the evolution of the markets in an agile way
- Promote ‘**real**’ **DSM** (standard data models, APIs) to allow SMEs to scale
- **Openness** should be promoted not only in theory to new business models, even if they disrupt existing business and require hard work by regulators
- **Harmonise ICT-related regulation**, and sector-specific regulatory environments (free flow of data, data ownership and legal frameworks (e.g. liability))
- Coordinate **skills development** efforts and engage digital innovation hubs

Link to the project website: <http://road2cps.eu/>

More information on the project outcomes can be found in the Road2CPS Ebook: <http://road2cps.eu/events/wp-content/uploads/2017/01/Road2CPS-EBook.pdf>

The Platforms4CPS Consensus Workshop presentation is available under the following link: https://www.platforms4cps.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/01_Road2CPS_Steinbeis_2i_RoadmapPitch.pdf

5.1.7 PICASSO (2017)

PICASSO (Towards New Avenues in EU-US ICT Collaboration), was a 24 month support action (January 2016 - June 2018) with the mission to enhance EU-US ICT research and innovation collaboration, to address societal challenges and industry needs and to enable economic growth in both the EU and US. Main themes of ICT pre-competitive RDI are the following key enabling technologies: 5G, Big Data, IoT/CPS. Application domains include smart production, smart cities, smart transport, smart energy.

Main research Priorities identified include:

Closing the loop in IoT-enabled Cyber-Physical Systems

- System-wide control via IoT-connected devices
- Data-based operation
- Control architectures for IoT-enabled CPS
- Performance and stability in the face of unpredictability (outages etc.)

Integration, interoperability, flexibility, and reconfiguration

- Semantic interoperability and semantic models
- Openness and open standards, harmonisation
- Automatic (re-)configuration and plug-and-play
- Shared infrastructure, large-scale pilots
- Architectures and cross-domain infrastructures

Model-based systems engineering

- Integrated, virtual, full-life-cycle engineering
- High-confidence CPS, validation, verification, risk analysis and risk management
- Models of heterogeneous large-scale systems

Trust, (cyber)security, robustness, resilience, and dependability

- Fault detection and mitigation
- Trustworthiness of technical systems
- Behaviour-based methodologies for trust
- New engineering perspectives
- Secure real-time and mixed-criticality systems

Autonomy and humans in the loop

- Autonomy in open systems that are not domain/knowledge-‘contained’
- Models of autonomous systems and humans
- Humans in the loop/collaborative decision making
- Analysis of user behaviour
- Analysis, visualisation, and decision support

Situational awareness, diagnostics, prognostics

- Large-scale data analytics, management
- Machine learning, adaptive behaviour
- Predictive maintenance
- Self-diagnosis tools

Link to the project website: <http://www.picasso-project.eu>

The Platforms4CPS Consensus Workshop presentation is available under the following link:

https://www.platforms4cps.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/04_PICASSO_TU_Dortmund_RoadmapPitch.pdf

5.1.8 ARTEMIS-SRA (2016)

(SRA first edition of 2006, update in 2011, addendum 2013, update 2016)

Powered by the new era of this Digital Transformation, ARTEMIS supports a vision where Europe remains among the world-class leaders in the area of Cyber-Physical Systems and Embedded Intelligence. ARTEMIS subscribes to achieving the 'Digital Single Market in Europe' by providing strong technological capability over the total value chain, and on both the supply side and the application side of Embedded Intelligence, thus closing the loop between market pull and technology push. Therefore, for the 2016 present Strategic Research Agenda ARTEMIS aims to fulfil a set of main objectives:

- Consolidate the **pathway of the digital revolution**
- Enable a more agile and shorter development cycle through the **adoption of design by composition and correct-by construction principles**
- **Overcome fragmentation** in the European supply base for the components and tools of design and engineering
- **Remove barriers between application contexts** to yield multi-domain, reusable components and systems
- Extend the use of **digital platforms** to build the **ecosystems** needed for accelerating the innovation and the creation of **new business models**

The following priority targets have been selected to guide the R&D programmes for the period (2017-2025) with the purpose of having greater impact and quick-to-markets results:

- Allowing the pace of product-family roll-out to be governed by business **needs** (rather than engineering limitations), such as increased connectivity, and gaining customer confidence, trust and acceptance by providing safe and secure products and protecting his privacy
- Getting **faster to market** by reducing the development cycle and development costs, and mastering the complexity
- **Increased efficiency**: easy user adoption and lower threshold of product introduction in the market
- **Improved sustainability**: by enhancing the products and systems ease of use, adopting multi-view system design (from conception to operation and services) as well as a reuse policy

The ARTEMIS-IA distinguishes three focus areas:

- Embedded and Cyber-Physical Systems
- Internet of Things
- Digital Platforms

The ARTEMIS-SRA 2016 follows a cross-domain approach, complemented by the development of common building blocks to make significant advances in design by composition.

Figure 10. ARTEMIS-SRA – cross-domain and building block approach

While the cross-domain perspective helps to overcome the plea of the silos effect between sectors the purpose of ‘building blocks’ is to increase development efficiency, enhance usability, for better and easier adoption of engineering methods and tools, and to provide a holistic products/systems view covering the whole life cycle, also from a system of systems perspective.

The following research priorities and implementation strategies are presented.

Research priorities	Priorities for implementation	Strategic recommendations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CPS architectures principles (reference design and architecture) • Digital platforms (CPS creating smart services) • Seamless connectivity and interoperability / IoT • Trust, security, robustness and dependability • Autonomy and cooperation • Design methods, tools, virtual engineering • CPSoS • Computational blocks (computing platforms and energy management for CPS) • Basic research, fundamental research 	<p>Make it happen, innovation environment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ARTEMIS-IA innovation concept • Research funding programmes • Centres of innovation excellence • Standards and standardisation • Education and training • Relationship with other relevant initiatives and PPPs • International dimension 	<p>To maximise impact and a return on investment in this field, the following challenges must be addressed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • De-verticalisation of technology solutions with CPS platforms that cut across the barriers between application sectors including mass consumer markets. • Convergence of actors along the value chain from suppliers of components and customised computing systems to system integrators and end users. • Creation of new CPS platforms for both vertical and core markets from automotive, health and energy to wireless communications and digital consumer products and services.

Table 6: ARTEMIS-SRA– selection of priority fields and recommendations

To maximise impact and a return on investment in this field, the following challenges must be addressed:

- De-verticalisation of technology solutions with CPS platforms that cut across the barriers between application sectors including mass consumer markets.
- Convergence of actors along the value chain from suppliers of components and customised computing systems to system integrators and end users.
- Creation of new CPS platforms for both vertical and core markets from automotive, health and energy to wireless communications and digital consumer products and services.

Link to the ARTEMIS-SRA: <https://artemis-ia.eu/documents.html> and for ARTEMIS, ECSEL and ECS document updates.

5.1.9 ECSEL-MASRIA (2017)

The ECSEL-MASRIA 2017 has a CPS specific chapter. CPS is seen as an enabling technology for the digital future. The main objectives to be targeted by future research are:

- Expand strong R&I potential, **overcome fragmentation** in European supply base, optimise investments and resources to yield multi-domain, reusable smart products and related services.
- Exploit the growing **‘internet economy’**, where human and machines interact and collaborate to provide new services and businesses responding to the strong demand of the **‘always connected society’**, based on **digital platforms and interoperable ecosystems** providing large streams of data and information, enabling acceleration of innovation and creation of new business models.
- **Master the complexity, ensuring safety and security** while reducing the cost of utilising powerful software intensive products/systems, encompassing System of Systems engineering and multi-disciplinary approaches, leveraging the potential of new information and communication networking techniques (softwarisation), data analytics, cloud, and enabling the development of dependable and robust, cognitive and collaborative autonomous systems.
- Enable a **more agile, shorter development cycle** through the adoption of design by composition, correct-by-construction principles and innovative architectures and verification methods, also suitable for **dependable solutions** ensuring for users a high level of trust, confidence and privacy.
- Provide support for related certification and standardisation activities and education & training.

The following research priorities and implementation strategies are presented.

Research priorities	Strategy and Innovation Accelerators
<p>Digital Platforms</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Models of Cyber-Physical Systems • Building services in smart spaces based on the capabilities of CPS • Common infrastructure in addition to M2M solution islands • Reference architectures and engineering platforms • Separation of concerns • Provision of common services • Efficient reuse and composability <p>Enabling Technologies for Autonomous, Adaptive, Cooperative CPS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safe and robust perception of environment • Continuously evolving, systems, learning and adaptive behaviour • Optimal control using autonomous CPS • Reliable and trustable decision making, mission and action planning • Human-machine interaction • Data analytics for decision support • Advanced methods and techniques for validation & verification, qualification & certification <p>Architectures Principles and Models for Safe and Secure CPS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Model driven engineering • Systems of systems (SoS) • Reference architectures • Multi-/many-core systems • Dependability ‘by design’, and enabling certification, resistance/resilience to external cyber-attacks • Answering fundamental challenges in CPS design <p>Computing Platforms incl. HW, SW and Communication</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coping with the complexity of heterogeneous, distributed computing elements • Energy efficiency • Techniques for continuously monitoring the performance • Development of specific accelerators for CPS functions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support cross-domain sharing of technologies and research through interoperable applications platforms and innovation ecosystems, by addressing technological needs across these sectors, and favouring the cross-fertilisation and consolidation of R&D&I investments from mass market to safety- and mission critical systems • Support ‘virtual vertical integration’ that encourages market leaders to define the conditions for successful business innovation building on emerging technological developments, and vice versa • Coordinate technological platform developments (hardware and manufacturing to system design and software engineering) that should become recognised de-facto standards • Foster emergence of vertical ecosystems contributing to and embracing standards, complementarity of the actors and solutions, scalability and interoperability. • A programme approach, with particular emphasis on developing interoperable platforms, using complementary instruments (focussed project and think big) <p>Priorities for Implementation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • De-fragmentation • Support interoperable ecosystem • Support digital platforms • Support standardisation and certification • Support education and training

Table 7: ECSEL-MASRIA – selection of priority fields, strategy and innovation accelerators

5.1.10 ECS-SRA (2018)

The ECS-SRA was issued in January 2018. It represents a common Strategic Research Agenda for the ECSEL JU Private Members AENEAS, ARTEMIS-IA and EPOSS. The rationale behind combining the previously separate roadmaps was to speak in one voice on the ‘Electronic Components and Systems’ (ECS) complete value chain and ensure that a right set of RD&I projects are generated.

Priority fields / ECS-SRA chapters	CPS related major challenges to be targeted by future research (selection)	Priorities for implementation
Technological <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Systems & components • Connectivity & interoperability • Safety & security & reliability • Electronics components & system process technology, equipment materials & manufacturing • Computing & storage 	Systems and components: architecture, design and integration <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Managing critical, autonomous, cooperating, evolvable systems • Managing complexity, diversity and multiple constraints • Miniaturisation, integration, increasing compactness Connectivity and interoperability <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meeting future connectivity requirements leveraging heterogeneous technologies • Enabling nearly lossless interoperability across protocols encodings and semantics • Ensuring secure connectivity and interoperability Safety, security and reliability <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensuring safety, security and privacy by design • Ensuring reliability and functional safety • Ensuring secure, safe and trustable connectivity and infrastructure • Managing privacy, data protection and human interaction Computing and storage <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increasing performance at acceptable cost • Making computing systems more integrated with the real world • Making "intelligent" machines • Developing new disruptive technologies: Quantum technologies, neuromorphic computing, optical computing. 	Innovation accelerators to make it happen <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardisation and regulation • Platforms and business models • Education and training • Supporting SMEs: from start-ups to scale-ups • Public procurement • Research infrastructures • Relationship with other relevant initiatives and PPPs • International cooperation

Table 8: ECS-SRA – selection of priority fields, major challenges and innovation accelerators

In more detail, the CPS related challenges regarding architecture, design and integration comprise:

Managing critical, autonomous, cooperating, evolvable systems

- Models, model libraries, and model based design technologies
- Verification and Validation (V&V) and test for critical systems: Methods and tools
- (virtual) engineering

Managing complexity

- Systems architecture
- System design
- Methods and tools to increase design efficiency
- Complexity reduction for V&V and test

Managing diversity

- Multi-objective optimisation of components and systems
- Modelling and simulation of heterogeneous systems
- Integration of analogue and digital design methods
- Connecting digital and physical world

Managing multiple constraints

- Ultra-low power design methods
- Efficient modelling, test and analysis for reliable, complex systems considering physical effects and constraints
- Safe systems with structural variability

5.2 Roadmap Consensus Themes

5.2.1 Research and Technology Priorities

The main **technological barriers** highlighted in many roadmaps are a lack of **interoperability** between components as well as systems, missing **standards** and resulting difficulties with the **integration** of legacy systems. Challenges regarding safety, stability, **dependability** and resilience of ‘always on’ and emerging CPS pose high demands to engineering and still present a bottleneck to wider exploitation. Moreover, mastering the ever-growing **complexity**, terminology, semantics and achieving cost-efficient verification, validation and testing is a big challenge.

The move towards **autonomous systems** raises many new questions, which will have to be answered not only by technological advances, but also by society. Systems that people can **trust** will be crucial for the success of future CPSs, especially those, whom we will allow to take decisions for us. Major concerns have also been identified regarding **security, privacy and confidentiality** issues. Research priority themes of great consensus between roadmaps, also confirmed by the Platforms4CPS workshop ^[12] ^[41] ^[42] ^[43] ^[44] were:

- **CPS engineering** of large, more and more complex systems and **model-based systems engineering** including integrated, virtual, full-life-cycle engineering, high-confidence CPS, validation, verification, risk analysis and risk management
- **Application of intelligent systems for SW- and systems engineering processes** including automated decision making in all lifecycle phases, and AI based analysis of development and runtime artefacts
- **Trustable AI-enabled autonomous CPS**, cognitive systems and situation awareness, diagnostics, prognostics and large-scale data analytics/decision support and explainable AI
- **Human-in-the-loop**, human as part of the system and HMI including **intuitive systems**, wearable and implantable systems, virtual and augmented reality as well as human machine collaboration and collaborative decision making
- **Integration, interoperability, flexibility, and reconfiguration** including semantic interoperability and models, openness and open standards, automatic (re-)configuration and plug-and-play
- **Agile, open plug and play CPS platforms**, vertical and horizontal digital technology platforms, federation of platforms, open interfaces, interoperability, reference architectures, standards
- **Safety, robustness, resilience, and dependability** including fault detection and mitigation for secure real-time and mixed-criticality systems, risk-based testing of autonomous/intelligent systems, fail-safe operation of intelligent/autonomous systems
- **Cybersecurity, privacy, trust** including blockchain, distributed ledgers digital identities, trusted and adaptive security architecture, co-engineered safety and security
- **Connectivity, computing and storage** seamless connectivity, hyper convergence and wireless intelligence, edge computing and edge cloud interactions, intelligent edge devices, new disruptive technologies including quantum technologies, cognitive computing, neuromorphic computing, brain inspired computing

5.2.2 Non-Technological Priorities and Innovation Accelerators

Next to research and technology priorities, many CPS roadmaps identify ‘non-technological’ priorities that can act as innovation accelerators or enablers for market adoption. The roadmaps specifically mentioned the following groups of innovation accelerators:

- **Overcoming fragmentation** in Europe through coordinated efforts
- **Enhancing collaboration** across domains and value chains and with related projects
- Building and sustaining a supportive and stimulating **innovation ecosystem**
- Elaborating **business models**
- Creating an **open business environment** with open data, architectures, platforms and standards as well as open innovation and open environments
- Facilitating **access to SMEs and start-ups**
- Providing research and service **infrastructure** as well as testing facilities and **demonstration**
- Clarifying issues on **law and regulation**, Single Digital Market
- Stimulating cross-disciplinary **education** and reskilling, educate society
- Raising societal awareness, **stimulate dialogue**, and enhance **user-acceptance**

In various Platforms4CPS workshops, participants were asked to identify and rank such non-technological priorities. This revealed the highest rankings for ecosystem & community building, education & training, open data, architectures & platforms, cross-disciplinary research and business models. Other important themes were collaboration on a regional, national and global scale, as well as demonstrators & living labs, regulation and legal issues, and the human-in-the-loop. Ethics and societal dialogue and awareness raising were also identified as important themes.

Figure 11. Selection of Non-Technological CPS Priorities, as voted by Digital Innovation Forum Participants

Deeper analysis of this ranking is shown in Figure 11 indicating the differences in perception considering the various stakeholders. Here it is noted that both Large Enterprises and SMEs scored business models highly. Ecosystem building, and collaboration were ranked highly by all stakeholders.

Challenges for the successful implementation of CPS are seen to be in the fragmentation of European efforts and initiatives as well as across application domains and value chains. There are also economic and business-related barriers, such as high implementation **costs**, missing **business models**, missing openness (open data) and fear of **vendor lock**. Supporting **legal frameworks, regulation, certification, IPR protection**, liability, are also not yet in place. **Conservatism**, resistance to change and missing **entrepreneurial** thinking are additional barriers. Access to technologies and infrastructures is seen as

difficult, especially for SMEs and start-ups. There are also scientific and educational challenges in bringing different scientific fields together to follow a multi-paradigm approach. This requires inclusion of aspects like business, law and ethics for a successful implementation. The lack of **skills**, knowledge, competences, **IT education** and interdisciplinarity are seen as major barriers. This requires an approach to lifelong learning and reskilling that can quickly adapt to the fast-changing environment. It was also highlighted strongly that mastering complexity, terminology, semantics and overcoming concerns regarding safety and stability will be crucial for the success of future CPS. Critically, **user acceptance** and trust need to be ensured and **ethical concerns** overcome. Without a deep and critical dialogue, positive vision and mindful path to implement such pervasive and partially autonomous systems, societal concerns might become the main showstopper to the uptake of the technology.

In terms of improving **market adoption**, there were a number of common requirements from different application domains. These include:

- Enhancing integration, standardisation, interoperability, modularity and flexibility of solutions
- Providing easy to use and easy to understand plug-and-play platforms based on shared standards
- Ensuring sustainability of the provided technology (upgradable, adaptable, flexible, in the context of the long-term oriented equipment investments)
- Fostering new business models and stimulating a culture of innovation/entrepreneurship
- Building up an innovation ecosystem and facilitate the integration of SMEs and innovators
- Implementing of open solutions, avoid vendor lock (change mind-set of relevant players)
- Reducing risk and implementation costs by providing demonstration, testing facilities, success stories and best practices
- Addressing safety, security and privacy issues as well as IP protection
- Elaborating of regulatory and legal frameworks for CPS and implementations in different domains
- Enhancing collaboration and reduce fragmentation of efforts, to match supply and demand
- Enhancing training and education as well as reskilling possibilities and attracting talent to the EU
- Raising awareness and interest in CPS and foster societal dialogue

6 Technology and Research Radar

Building on the Consensus Roadmap Themes a **Technology and Research Radar** has been developed, and confirmed within various workshops ^[43] ^[44] exploring CPS emerging technologies and research priorities in the specific fields to derive recommendations for future research programs focusing on timeframes from today until 2020, between 2020 and 2030 and beyond 2030. The Technology and Research Radar (see Figure 12) is sub-divided into eight key technological domains that capture new emerging themes within CPS:

- Data analytic and decision support
- Autonomy and robotics
- CPS Engineering
- CPS Architectures
- CPS Platforms
- Safety, security, privacy, trust
- Human as part of the system
- Communication and Computing

Key themes include ‘autonomous systems’, ‘Artificial Intelligence’ and ‘trust’. The radar identifies the need for research into new or improved **CPS engineering approaches** to manage and integrate increasingly complex systems with functionalities from multiple domains, including electrical, mechanical, physical engineering, computer science and communication. Increasingly this is being supported by the development of ‘digital twins’ to analyse and monitor a CPS at design and runtime. At a higher level these are being connected in continuously operated, maintained, and evolving Cyber-Physical Systems-of-Systems (CPSoS) with high demands for dependability, including safety, security, reliability, etc. Here there is a need for scientifically grounded and validated approaches for the design, development, and operation of CPS that supports the composition and interaction between sub-systems considering non-functional system requirements and legacy components. Supporting design tools and methods will need to be extended to integrate the different disciplines relevant for CPS, and in particular the domain of Artificial Intelligence, to ensure that key properties are met such as safety, security, reliability, and trustworthiness. This is particularly relevant for the certification of CPS and the acceptance of CPS by users and citizens in general.

The future depends on the use and exploitation of data and here there is a need for openness, with open data and federated agile open **platforms** to enable open innovation. The importance of interoperability (technical, syntactic, semantic, organisational), **CPS architectures and platforms** whether proprietary, open source, vertical, horizontal or business to business will increase. Looking further in the future, it is expected that dynamic islands of platforms will come together temporarily to provide services with a trend for increased decentralisation towards the edge, autonomy, orchestration, more connectivity, and agnostic connectivity with respect to vendors and protocols.

A vast amount of (real-time) information is becoming available and citizens are more informed and empowered to participate and take decisions. This is driving **data analytics**, data fusion and decision support. Expert Systems are being revolutionised via the use of AI, e.g. deep learning, and centralised cloud-based systems exploiting large amounts of data are already making headlines. Interactions with humans are being changed via semi-integration of cobots and personal AI assistants. AI is also being exploited in Cognitive CPS, for example in systems that can analyse their own behaviour and self-optimize their processes according to changing requirements, observations, or context. The future foresees AI being exploited at the edge requiring specialised, low power hardware such as neuromorphic processors and in the longer-term quantum processors. It is also expected that hand-held devices will partly be replaced by wearables or even implantable devices.

The interaction and collaboration between **CPS and humans** will intensify through the use of intuitive interfaces, assisting systems and humanoid robots. The human will become a functional part of the system, with fusion between CPS and human enabled brain-computer interfaces. Future systems will have to predict and adapt to human needs, preferences and capabilities. Research and development will have to cross the silos with respect to disciplines, but also application domains. Cross fertilisation between disciplines such as biology and computing, ethics and engineering will be key.

With the increased use of autonomy, levels of human control will change. This drives the need for understandable, accountable autonomous systems, which act ethically and where liability questions have been solved. Society will need to be educated to live in the new digital world. Education and training will be essential to allow users to build trust in “trustworthy CPS”. At the same time T-shape (broad and deep) education as well as lifelong learning and reskilling will become a focus to avoid the digital divide and to allow workers to adjust to new job profiles.

6.1 Details on Topics and Timelines

6.1.1 Interoperability and Platforms

Platforms landscape. The **current landscape is fragmented with** a mix of **vertical** and **horizontal platforms** some of which are **open** and some of which are **closed**. Vendors are keen to provide large monolithic platforms such as MindSphere and GE Predix with the aim of dominating the market but industry is concerned about **vendor lock-in**. There are thus many **proprietary platforms** but fewer **open source platforms**. The *trend beyond 2020*, however, is towards **horizontal platforms** and **business to business to platforms** (business models playing an important role). Further in the future, *in the 2030 timescale*, it is expected that **dynamic islands of platforms** will come together temporarily to provide services, e.g. management of the grid. An advantage of this approach is that they can be disconnected from other connected islands in response to a cyber-attack on part of the grid.

Interoperability. With respect to **interoperability**, we are still at an early stage and a number of different approaches at applications level and other levels have been tried. For instance, the Unify-IoT project identified six levels of interoperability including, **technical, syntactic, semantic, organisational**, etc. However, most approaches to interoperability are still at a centralised level. Here the EC has promoted the creation of “Android type” platforms for industry, however, the move of Microsoft to provide an Open Source Azure platform might well make this platform the **de-facto platform** for the future. Key issues that need addressing are **safety, security and integration of legacy**. As systems are heterogeneous, interoperability is an absolute must. An example of this is automated braking for cars in a platoon where it will be necessary to send messages between cars from different manufacturers. Of course, there will also be a need for a backup system, c.f. as the human does when brake lights fail when other visual cues are used. The overall *trend* is towards **seamless interoperability** so that it is possible to buy **cheap plug-and-play components**.

Federation. There is a need for **federated platforms** across stakeholder administrative domains. An example of this are the owners of autonomous vehicles that will want to connect to infrastructure owners. For business reasons parties will want to keep ownership of these separate and they will come together via a Service Level Agreement. Enablers will also be needed to aggregate and filter data to provide services. This will result in decentralised SLAs and services. Trust and reputation will be very important in this and platforms will need a good reputation in order to support safety-critical applications. Looking further in the *future* **ledger-based platforms** will be important.

Other important areas for the *future* will be **agile and dynamic platforms, plug-and-play platform composition and autonomy**. Potential applications include an electric car, which can be left at a train station. This can be plugged in to be charged up during the day but could also be used as a source of power at peak times, e.g. to power station services such as cafeterias to smooth electrical load. It would also be possible to go one stage further than this and use cars as processor platforms so that owners can make money from them while they are parked, perhaps via bitcoin mining.

Edge Computing. Overall, it was noted that there is a general *trend* from **static to dynamic platforms** with more and **more decentralisation**. In *future* we need to be able to **federate platforms**. The **edge** is becoming increasingly important as highlighted by the EC. Most platforms today are centralised with attached edge components. Things are moving towards **decentralisation of processing to the edge** and this can be used to optimise energy as processing is performed much closer to the physical point of interaction. It is also possible to think about **opportunistic temporary connections** that would allow new functionality or services.

Business Ecosystems. With respect to **business ecosystems**, new business models are needed. The cloud-based model is used at the moment but as **things move to the edge** the business models change. Some thought needs to be placed on how to achieve monetisation, on ownership and also how value is generated. Today companies are talking about **selling an experience**. An example is music where we now download a tune and play it whereas before we would physically buy media with the recorded music, which we would then keep. So, it is now about the experience and providers need to provide the best experience for customers so that they will pay for it and also return for more. One critical requirement for the future will be a **trusted CPS multi-sided marketplace (and ecosystem)**.

In conclusion, there are a number of *trends*, such as **increased decentralisation, autonomy, orchestration, more connectivity, and agnostic connectivity** with respect to the vendor and protocols. It will be necessary to change platforms in response to **AI** and, in particular, there will be a move from centralised AI in the cloud to decentralised AI at the edge. Therefore, there is a need for **platforms that support AI at the edge, neuromorphic processors**, and in the longer-term, **quantum processors**.

6.1.2 Autonomy and Robotics

The general trends are clear, with CPS becoming gradually more autonomous and collaborative (including with other systems as well as humans) – taking on more sophisticated physical tasks in increasingly unstructured environments. This progression is driven by the availability of better sensors (perception) and communication networks, detection and reasoning capabilities (including through AI and machine learning) and improved computational capabilities (on-board as well as off-board systems) – enabling more complex actions to be achieved.

For autonomous systems *in 2020* - **object identification** is expected to be quite a mature technology, which will contribute to many new advancements. Examples include choosing between ally and foe or identification of the environment such as changes resulting from different seasons (rain and sun can cause different dynamics). Two other technologies that will be in significant use are **miniaturised low-cost sensors** and **energy harvesting**, these will be significant enablers for working in remote environments. A key hurdle will be the use of such technologies in safety/mission critical systems due to the current lack of methods to provide assurance in some form of the reliability/availability/failure modes. This means for instance **deep learning**, where optimisation occurs based on previous events, is likely to be restricted initially to non-critical areas.

In the near future (2020-2030), there will be significant developments related to self-maintenance. This will result from advances in **self-diagnosis** capabilities, **real-time monitoring** and **predictive maintenance**. For instance **self-healing** will see sensors being able to clean themselves from dust, or the system recovering after a part breaks. This particularly applies to actuators, which are even more likely to get damaged because they interact with the environment and the capacity to repair themselves will be a great enabler – especially in application such as for deep sea or space. The **digital twin, supplemented by embedded AI**, will play an important role, where the system maintains a virtual model of itself and the environment.

Furthermore, there will be **self-reconfigurable modular robots** being able to adapt their physical structure and behaviours to different environments including new untested conditions. This links also to **self-learning** and **analysis of user behaviours** – the systems are out there doing different tasks and able to learn while they are carrying their actions. Depending on where operation takes place, there are safety concerns because if the machine is learning on the job it can introduce unforeseen

behaviours. Especially in the case of **cobots**, interacting closely with humans, it may mean learning would be required to take place in test environments. It is also believed we shall be seeing **new types of sensors and actuators** bringing new functionalities to systems. For gravity sensors currently under development – gravity changes around the earth and this can be used to provide maps as an alternative to GPS and opens ground for many new capabilities and technologies.

With respect to 2030 and onwards it is believed that **full autonomy for current needs** would be solved by 2045. Note that by that point new needs will have arisen as the systems and capabilities evolve and perhaps in 200 years we may still be aiming for full autonomy. An example would be systems having different types of missions to achieve on different days and may attach different sensors or new actuators to achieve different types of roles or context. Another point for 2030 was **full machine-to-machine collaboration** - this is where the machines are working with each other. It links to **full autonomous, adaptive cooperative CPS** capability (for current needs) this is a case where when the machine has many different choices it will react in the optimal way.

Another point linked with machine-to-machine collaboration is with respect to communication – should humans also be able to understand the communication taking place between the machines? This includes argumentation and symbolic analysis for machines coming to a consensus, this may include the system developing its own language to represent objects and symbols to represent things and concepts and arguing with other machines. This is functionality to an extent already in place and over next 10 years will mature to be used at quite a high level. Strong functionalities will be established so that systems can **self-organise** to best respond to environmental events with significant capability to manage expected and unexpected **emergent behaviours**. This also relates to systems being provided with **cognitive capability** for reasoning through problems and how this relates to them by **artificial consciousness**.

6.1.3 Data Analytics and Decision Support

This aspect aids in particular collaboration and coordination of interacting systems and people. Data analytics usually considers large quantities of data that, for example, may be related to optimising system components used in 1000s of products, or monitoring a natural disaster. **Decision support** is then based on the data and provides recommendations to the human users, for instance about beneficial modifications to components or send drones to aid with disaster relief.

Mature technologies for the period until 2020 include **machine learning** and the related pattern analysis for **real time (big) data analysis**. Additionally, **Expert Systems** were seen to be contributing significantly – these are systems that are trained through feedback from human experts, who indicate their choices in particular situations, which may then be abstracted to other contexts. These enable **safe and robust perception of the environment**. Finally, **data fusion** is a very mature and used technology already that is providing significant benefits.

After the next 10 years or so, much more technology is expected for **information extraction** from data and particularly **AI-enabled filtered information extraction**. It is also believed that system self-monitoring and **deep analysis data mining** such as improvement in production would be maturing in this period. This is likely to be supported for instance by maturing **neural network technology** (with application of course in other areas too). It is used already to an extent in general systems, for instance Rolls Royce install sensors for live feedback of operational systems, but there is a higher degree of complexity for autonomous systems. Analyses of behaviours/problems/solutions would be communicated back to the manufacturing facility then applied in subsequent updates. It was noted to

be particularly the case for car manufacturers where On-board Diagnostics (OBD) ports will be scrapped and data monitoring will be transferred to the cloud and accessible to garages in relation to competition laws in Europe.

Algorithms for identifying which information to collect will be needed. This is important because much irrelevant data is being collected and data storage contributes to pollution. The challenge is how you get a balance between data, which is useful and data that is not useful especially in cases where only time can tell. For instance if a harmful accident occurs more data may help explain why it happened. However, data should be used as optimally as possible because it is a consumer of energy and thus generator of CO₂. Additionally algorithms should provide **filtering against corrupt data** and data is expensive to transfer, so we should only be sending key information except for unusual circumstances. There is also a risk of "Fake News", which also applies to machine systems and requires advanced **situational awareness** and **collaborative decision making** functionalities.

After 2030 miniaturisation of data centres with reduced energy consumption come into play – enabling **minimum data but maximum relevance**. In addition, knowledge transfer will reach maturity – either between systems, for instance to pass on knowledge or for gaining it in one context and then transferring it for use in another context. This will contribute to human **trustable decision making, mission and action planning**. **Ethics** plays a pivotal role. Should CPS systems have the capability decide on whom to kill in an accident? For example in a car accident, should the autonomous vehicle decide on killing the driver by driving toward the obstacle or drive into the crowd (e.g. pedestrians on the sidewalk)? This remains a question to be solved, but trust of the general public and acceptance of the systems is important, which should be supported by reasoning through **predictive and cognitive CPS**.

6.1.4 Human in the Loop

This section is related to how people interact with CPS. Looking at 2020, the **semi-integration of cobots** is identified as maturing since already there are situations with **people physically interacting with machines** in operation but it's believed there is not yet 100% reliability. Full integration likely to be after 2030. Technologies related to **displays, speech recognition, voice assistants and image processing** are well matured and to be built upon.

For next few years **user interface adaptability** will still be maturing but providing many capabilities, where the interface changes depending on the context and also depending on the purpose. For instance if the person was handicapped with blindness, the system could change to non-visual interfaces. Changing contexts can also imply different visual methods such as a desktop monitor or mobile phone, even this is still not 100% solved. Technologies maturing to assist here include: **gesture screens, augmented reality, ambient intelligence**. In addition, it is believed that **training interactions** will become significantly more advanced in this timeframe. For example, systems physically watching people perform a task and then repeating it themselves. This will be supported by technologies including **object recognition, wearables and computer vision**. **Virtual assistants** are likely to provide services such as personalised intermediary translators (person to machine) managing different accents and languages for machines to understand. Much technology already exists for voice recognition and translation as a stepping stone for this application. It would enable interaction with many digital services (so the assistant acts as a connector to all digital services enabling services to not require independent learning mechanisms for human speech). Note that this would not apply to discussions between people because accents play an import role at this level.

Following on from 2030, there will be qualitative association of **human emotions feedback** for determining satisfaction level with tasks completed by the system – supported by **fully interactive social robotics** and **robots with personalities**. Another aspect that will need time to reach maturity is **laws and regulation** for types of CPS interaction such as autonomous drones flying through the countryside, city or other regions. Finished with **reliability of the autonomous systems** – full reliability believed to be achieved in 2030. New methods of interaction will have matured including **neural-control interfaces** and **bio-inspired mechanisms**.

Trust was seen as an important factor across many segments, but especially when the human becomes part of the system – humans trusting machine, machines trusting other machines – but there is also now machines trusting humans – for instance, an autonomous car may detect unusual behaviour in a human-driven car (perhaps illness or alcohol related) and adjust its actions accordingly. Another recurring cross-cutting theme relates to security and safety. Thus, engineering techniques for adjusting to context while maintaining trust, safety and security in these systems will provide acceleration for the adoption of new technologies.

6.1.5 CPS (Virtual) Engineering

CPS Engineering is concerned with scientifically grounded and validated approaches to the **design, development, and operation of CPS**. The key reason for the need of engineering for any type of system is to cope with complexity. CPS come with a dramatic increase of **complexity** in various ways, for instance because they integrate systems and functionality from **multiple domains**, including electrical, mechanical, physical engineering, computer science and communication. CPS are often forming **Systems of Systems (CPSoS)**, have **high demands** regarding dependability, including safety, security, reliability, etc., and need to be continuously operated, maintained, and evolved.

Being able to analyse a CPS is important both for the **design time** and during **runtime**. CPS constituent systems are built to specific requirements and dedicated purposes, but typically, the overall behaviour of a CPS is created from the **composition and interaction of its sub-systems**. In order to develop resilient, safe, and secure CPS it is necessary to understand those interactions and analyse the **emerging behaviour** of the CPS, so that engineering becomes aware of such **non-functional system requirements**. More generally, there is the challenge of integrating cross-cutting aspects such as safety and security of the system or the consideration of the human as a key factor for CPS into the engineering process. It is key to take such cross-cutting aspects into account from the very beginning, and hence appropriate processes are needed to support **safety-security co-engineering**. Furthermore, **Artificial Intelligence (AI)**, which is considered a key technology for future smart CPS, needs to be made amenable to engineering as a discipline. For example, AI technologies such as machine learning are used in a black box fashion, while at the same time it will be necessary to engineer such components in a way that they can be used as building blocks of CPS, with specified capabilities that can be verified and certified to ensure trust.

As CPS are **complex, often large and expensive** systems it is necessary that analyses can be performed before the concrete system is being built, i.e. at design time, by **simulating the system behaviour at model level**. Several challenges are related to this, such as to scale current simulation and analysis methods and tools to cope with the systems size of envisaged CPSs, the need to integrate design methods from the various engineering disciplines involved in building CPS, understanding the function and behaviour of standard or legacy components, e.g. COTS technology, or supporting the full product life cycle. Simulation and analyses are also important when the system is being deployed, to **monitor**

runtime operations, detect potential mal-function or unanticipated context changes. Here there is a need to be able to map the observed behaviour to the model level, including system requirements and safety cases, so as to understand when a system deviates from its intended behaviour, and to identify and eliminate potential causes. Developing fully virtual copies of a CPS, so-called "**digital twins**", allow for analysing deviating behaviour by replaying it on virtual systems. Furthermore, effects of updating or replacing constituent parts of a CPS can be analysed and tested in advance on the digital twin.

A key topic where further research is needed relates to the multi-disciplinary character of CPS. There is a need to develop enabling technologies and corresponding design tools and methods that **integrate the different disciplines relevant for CPS**, and in particular the domain of **Artificial Intelligence**. Further research is also needed for engineering methods and design tools that address the **highly dynamic nature of complex CPS or systems of CPS**, where (sub-) systems dynamically form and collaborate in larger systems, and act in uncertain contexts and environments. In this regard, managing how **CPS sub-systems of agile and intelligent devices can be composed** both during the design time, but also and more importantly during run-time is a key area where further work is needed.

6.1.6 CPS Architectures

A major challenge for CPS is the need to ensure **key properties** such as safety, security, reliability, and **trustworthiness**. Architectures are needed that enable such non-functional properties to be designed, and established and maintained during run-time. However, today we see **historically grown architectures** in various domains such as infrastructures or production that provide only limited safety guarantees. The challenge how to **evolve these architectures** to support CPS needs to be tackled. In addition to that, architectures and platforms need to support the **assessment of their safety and security properties** and allow for testability. This is particular relevant with regard to **certification of CPS**, and to enable **acceptance of CPS** by users, or citizens in general. The *trend* to move **data analytics and decision functions to the edge of CPS** has to be reflected in architecture designs, combining both the embedded world and cloud systems. As CPS are typically built from various constituent systems, and may be formed dynamically during run-time, it is generally impossible to collect and describe all relevant information about the environment or context in which a (sub-system) CPS will be used. Related to this, data gathered by the sensor systems of a CPS may not always be able to completely and consistently describe the current situation a CPS is acting in. Hence, CPS need to be able to run in unknown contexts and with uncertain information. Architecture must provide mechanisms that **enable CPS to create a context-awareness**, reacting and adapting to changing environments and situations. Similarly, it is necessary that adaption mechanisms be **predictable and understandable**. Architectures are needed that support the distributed and cooperative execution of functions, or even the **collaborative learning of CPS**. Another aspect is that CPS, once deployed will need to run continuously, without interruptions. Hence, improvements or evolutions of CPS have to occur while the systems are running. Consequently, architectures must **support such evolving systems**.

Beyond 2030: Looking further into the future, we may see CPS that have certain capabilities to understand parts of their functioning and can act upon this understanding. **Cognitive CPS**, for example can analyse their own behaviour and assess the needs to optimise their processes according to changing requirements, observations, or context. Taking this further we can imagine **autopoietic systems** that have the capability to maintain, reassemble, or reproduce themselves. For such self-evolving or even self-reproducing systems there will be a need to provide adequate descriptions mechanisms, such as **self-referential** or **meta-models for CPS and architectures**, that describe the structure and behaviour of a CPS and in which ways it can be changed or adapted. Mechanisms to

decide which adaptations are needed to optimise functionality or structure of CPS may be supported by AI algorithms, leading to something we could call '**AI-aided engineering**'.

6.1.7 Safety, Security, Privacy, Trustworthiness and Compliance

Until 2020, a **framework for legislation** is required on key CPS issues, like GDPR. In the same vein, a **framework for trustworthiness** as well as **education and training** will be essential to allow users to build trust towards CPS. A framework should help to define, e.g. through certification, what a dependable and reliable system is.

Between 2020 and 2030, **blockchain** will be one mean to make systems trustworthy, although it hinders privacy. **Transparency and privacy by design** already exist but it will gain in importance. Indeed **ethics** will affect the debates of the next decade regarding CPS and AI. Consequently, privacy, security, and safety will have to be **included by design and co-engineered**, which will imply a strong dependency towards CPS architectures. **Biometrics** can be a very dangerous technology if not properly secured, since biometric data can be copied and give access to personal information. Once biometric data are converted into digital format they can be copied and used by impersonators. As a matter of fact, using biometric data (e.g. a fingerprint, eye's retina...) as a login is equivalent to use a password that cannot be changed. Therefore, in case it is hacked it gives access to all information previously protected and can be used for further stealing the identification of the person. In order to continue to use biometrics a "really" secure solution has to be found or this technology will have to be abandoned until 2030.

Importantly, **safety and security** are converging together, because of the rise in new IT systems that interact with humans. A framework must be developed for the cybersecurity of systems that need to be safe to avoid harming human beings. Inspiration could be found in the way by which GDPR established a **cybersecurity framework** around the protection of electronic personal data. Accordingly, a **regulation about the safety of IT products and services** must be developed and include a cybersecurity framework ensuring that fines and penalties will be imposed in case a cyber-incident is at the origin of a safety incident.

Post quantum security solutions should continue to be investigated, based on advanced mathematics and algorithms. Security of the whole supply chain (from supplier to customer) as well as cyber forensic (criminal investigation) have to be developed.

Finally, AI is a powerful tool to detect suspicious behaviours and activities as well as to develop **resistant CPS to cyber-attacks**; the downside is that AI generate ever more cyber-attacks. Therefore, AI data and systems will have to be perfectly protected, given the increasing dependency of CPS on automated decisions (**autonomous CPS**).

Beyond 2030, the challenge will be to guaranty **trustworthy, safe and secure CPS**, while they will steadily gain in complexity and ever more interact with humans (**human in the loop and cooperating CPS**). For this, research at the **intersection of AI and cybersecurity** should be pushed.

7 Themes for Future Research and Innovation Programmes

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7.1 Trends

Regarding the technology trends and new/emerging themes **autonomous systems** become very prominent in connection with **Artificial Intelligence** and **trust**. There is a need for understandable, accountable autonomous systems, which act ethical and where liability questions have been solved. Next to data-driven CPS basing their decisions on analytics by deep learning and new AI methods, neurocognitive systems and brain-inspired computing will be challenges ahead. Moreover, hand held devices will partly be replaced by wearables or even implantable devices. The interaction and **collaboration between CPS and humans** will be intensified (intuitive, assisting systems, humanoid robots), the human becoming a functional part of the system, towards **the fusion between CPS and the human** enabled brain-computer interfaces.

New or improved (virtual) **CPS engineering** approaches to manage the more and more **complex systems** including the **human as a part**, but also **co-engineered safety, security and ethics** as a part of it are discussed intensively. Future system will have to predict and adapt to human needs, preferences and capabilities. Research and development will have to cross the silos, regarding disciplines but also application domains. Cross fertilisation (biology and computing, ethics and engineering) will be key.

In terms of societal and economic trends IT-systems tend to become **addictive**, with an enhanced dependence of society on these, but at the same time an increasing vulnerability (and urge for safety and security of such systems). A vast amount of (real-time) information becomes available and citizens become more informed and empowered to participate and take decisions. **Openness**, open data, federated agile open platforms and open innovation became more prominent topics over the last years. **Business models** become more decoupled from ownership, and topics like servitisation, data driven economy, sharing economy, crowd funding, blockchain are arising. Products become more and more individualised and customers become more involved in co-designing them. Educating society, professional T-shape (broad and deep) **education** as well as lifelong learning and reskilling will become a focus to avoid the **digital divide**.

7.2 Emerging Research Themes

Platforms4CPS has identified a number of emerging themes for the future including the need to master ‘autonomous systems’, exploit ‘Artificial Intelligence’ and provide ‘trust’ as well as maintaining sovereignty in key value chains.

A key challenge identified by CPS experts was how to **manage complexity** at both the design stage and in the operation of systems to provide trustworthy systems for the future. Engineers need to deal with many heterogeneous components and also complex **interactions with humans**. This requires new approaches to systems engineering that can deal with decomposition into components to manage complexity and new or improved CPS engineering approaches.

Gaining a lead in ‘**edge computing**’ was also identified as a major opportunity for Europe. Many systems are relying on cloud computing and big data processing at the moment, however, the ability to move processing to local assets allows systems to react promptly in time-critical applications, e.g. autonomous driving. Here the latency of remote connections to central cloud processing would not be acceptable for safety and predictability of response. This coupled with increasing concerns over privacy and security makes edge processing highly advantageous. Successful exploitation of edge computing, however, requires development and demonstration of high performance computing, energy efficient computation for battery and energy harvesting powered operation and new computing techniques such as neuromorphic computing.

Humans are an integral part of the system and may interact with the system in a number of ways raising fundamental questions on the degree of automation required and how CPS and humans collaborate. There is also a move from hand held devices to wearables or even implantable devices. The interaction and collaboration between CPS and humans will thus intensify with intuitive, assisting systems and humanoid robots. In future systems will have to predict and adapt to human needs, preferences and capabilities. Research and development will thus have to cross silos with respect to disciplines such as biology, computing, ethics and engineering in a variety of application domains.

Within CPS diverse functions are integrated to meet systems-level attributes such as safety, security, performance and usability. Above this there is a need for **co-engineering** to link the system attributes to manage traceability in the product lifecycle and deal with trade-offs between conflicting attributes. Here automation can be used to deal with complexity management, in particular, to track the impact of system changes during the product lifecycle. For instance, to alert design experts that performance or safety may be compromised by a security patch or via addition of new technology, e.g. from an SME. Here there are strong linkages with incremental certification and agile system engineering.

7.3 Future Research and Innovation Programmes

In the **short term (Horizon 2020)** the European Commission should build upon existing activities and target actions that lead to a synchronisation of National Initiatives, PPPs and large-scale pilots. At a national level member states have already started initiatives like ‘Industry 4.0’ in Germany ^[2], ‘Smart Industry’ in the Netherlands ^[17], ‘L’industrie du Futur’ in France ^[32] or the ‘High Value Manufacturing Catapult’ in the UK ^[53]. Here there are already major investments in the PPPs and large-scale pilots and there is a desire to promote cross-coordination between these to address vision areas such as autonomous cars, health, etc. This is already beginning via the lighthouse projects initiated by the PPPs.

The EC has put in place actions shown under Horizon 2020 ^[27] to support partnerships and platforms, the regulatory framework, Digital Innovation Hubs to engage with SMEs, and digital skills. The strategy being adopted is fully supported by the findings of Platforms4CPS. It is clear that there is a need for greater cooperation between Member States and a need to synchronise existing and emerging regional, national and EC digitisation efforts. This has a major multiplier effect for Europe.

Digital Innovation Hubs. There is a strong need to engage with SMEs and support innovation and transfer of technology to SMEs. The most appropriate means for achieving this is via Digital Innovation Hubs ^[24], clusters and regional initiatives. The ‘Digital Innovation Hubs’ are seen as an important step forward for mastering digital transformation, where companies, particularly SMEs, can gain experience and insight on novel development of cutting edge technologies and have the chance to turn these developments into opportunities for their business. Overall, the European Commission should foster co-ordination of national and regional initiatives to bring together all relevant constituencies from EU Member States with the aim of creating an EU-wide network of Digital Innovation Hubs.

Digital Platforms and Standards. The adoption of European platforms and federation between existing platforms is seen as key for European industry and for accelerating the uptake of CPS implementation. In this area investment under Horizon 2020 in areas such as Digital Manufacturing, Agriculture, Smart Hospital of the Future & Smart and Healthy Living at Home, Internet of Things for Energy (Smart Homes and Grids), and 5G for Connected and Automated Driving is likely to have a major impact on key sectors of industrial importance to Europe. This should also be broadened to other areas where currently there are a lack of platforms that can be exploited by SMEs such as in the Construction Sector. The uptake of new platforms within the SME ecosystem should be encouraged by further actions via the ‘Digital Innovation Hubs’. Here it is recommended that further showcase experiments and large-scale pilots are funded to bring together key actors and critical mass. Strongly linked to this area is the need to harmonise and synchronise standardisation activities across Europe as a myriad of standards currently exist. Here the various field labs and pilots are seen as a very good way of testing new standards.

Supporting Regulatory Framework. The future will be strongly driven by the exploitation of data. Here there are a number of barriers and industry is looking for guidance in a number of areas. The GDPR regulation which was introduced in March 2018 is seen as a very positive step by industry providing much needed guidance. It is also important in allaying societal fears about loss of privacy and how personal data is being used. Further actions by the European Commission in development of the Data Package which covers the free flow of non-personal data, access and reuse of data and access of private data for public purposes is also likely to open up new business opportunities ^[28]. This will be further supported by the PSI directive ^[20] also known as European legislation on the re-use of public sector information which is trying to make as much business data, government data and scientific data as possible available to European companies.

Within the CPS domain, the areas of AI and autonomous systems are rapidly developing areas and it is expected that these will be key areas in the future. To support these areas there is a need for regulation to address liability issues. Currently, existing regulation in this area is being scrutinised such as that for the liability of defective products and services, as well as safety according to Machinery Directive 2006/42/EC ^[44], however, it is clear that as these fields develop there will be a need for more regulation to cover such areas as accidents in autonomous driving and to ensure the transparency of AI. Cybersecurity has also become a major concern for industry as a result of recent high-profile attacks. Certification for cybersecurity is thus a key need and this is being addressed via introduction of the European Cybersecurity Certificates Scheme ^[21]. Within this generalised overall framework specific

cybersecurity mechanisms will be defined for specific products. The area of security is currently a key concern for many companies engaged in development of CPS and is an area that is seen key for the future adoption.

In conjunction with the CPS foundations activities (<https://www.platforms4cps.eu/resources/> - Deliverable D4.3), it is believed future roadmapping activities could be supported by a global view of what parts and the extent to which CPS was treated in related research projects.

In the **longer term (Horizon Europe)**, from 2020 onwards, research and innovation activities will be supported by the new Framework Programme Horizon Europe ^[29]. Ideas for this programme are currently under development and there are many consultations taking place. There is an emphasis on missions ^[38] which target ‘moonshot’ activities and it is expected that funded projects will contribute to these missions. An example of a mission related to CPS is ‘an integrated transport system reducing car congestion by 50% in 10 European cities by 2030’. Several other of the proposed missions also address CPS topics.

Emerging Themes - There are a number of emerging themes that have been identified within Platforms4CPS workshops. The areas of ‘autonomous systems’, ‘Artificial Intelligence’ and ‘trust’ were clearly highlighted as key themes for the future. There is a need to support this by investigations and proposals for migrating existing CPS including business models. Furthermore funding should be provided for low power processing at the edge and a concerted action to master AI at a European level ^{[36] [37] [54]}. In order to build trustable systems of the future there is a need to maintain sovereignty of key value chains.

Processing at the Edge - There is a move towards localised intelligence at the ‘edge’ in order for CPS to react promptly in time-critical applications. It is not possible to guarantee safety, latency and predictability for autonomous cars if there is a reliance on remote connection to the cloud, so processing needs to be performed locally. Privacy and security concerns also drive the need for processing data at the edge rather than transmitting or storing data in the cloud. Notably edge computing is more amenable for privacy/security and is also GDPR compliant. In order to provide high performance computing and new computing techniques, such as neuromorphic computing, at the edge there is a need for energy efficient computation for battery powered and energy harvesting powered devices as well as for electric vehicles. This will require a 2-3 orders of magnitude improvement in energy consumption.

AI and Autonomous Systems - There is a need for understandable, accountable autonomous systems, which act ethically. Already there is an initiative to support an ‘AI-on-demand platform’ ^[25] with a desire to connect and strengthen AI activities across Europe. However, with the importance of AI for the future there is a need to provide even greater support for AI developments in key sectors. A positive step is that a declaration of cooperation on AI has been signed by 25 European Countries, which will produce a coordinated plan for AI by the end of 2018 ^[26]. AI will have major implications on future systems and European businesses require the necessary tools and skills to adopt and exploit AI-based solutions. In particular, a programme is required to encourage the business adoption of AI technologies to solve problems and deliver practical business value. In addition to adopting/developing AI solutions Europe must develop expertise and provide help in building investment and business cases. Governments and employers need to encourage and provide continual education and training for existing employees throughout their careers to encourage the development of skills in AI. The skills to develop and deploy AI solutions depend upon Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics

(STEM) skills and so there is a need provide incentives to pursue these areas particularly at the further education level with support from industry in the development of curricula.

Trust and acceptance - Trust is difficult to build and given a majority of CPS are safety-critical, it is one of the biggest impediments for integrating new technologies. It relates to both manufacturers and the Public. In order to generate trust for future CPS there has been a call for a factor of 10 reduction in software bugs, a requirement for better usability, a need for resistance to cyber-attacks, and an approach to explainable AI technologies. Already complexity is a challenge, but tools will be required to improve the productivity of companies to produce dependable software automation systems, robots and AI. There also needs to be a public debate on ethics and trust with involvement from government, academia and industry as well as the general public.

Sovereignty - There is growing concern over sovereignty across key value chains, e.g. Aerospace and Automotive, as the political climate in the world is changing fast. There are two key threats. The first is that if Europe becomes reliant on foreign hardware and software in key value chains then restrictions on exporting products to other countries may prevent European trade. More seriously, if systems rely on foreign made components it will not be possible to guarantee safety and security of future systems. There are increasing concerns about security issues from backdoors in the hardware, which may lead to systems and infrastructure being compromised by foreign governments and terrorists. There is thus a pressing need for full European sovereignty in key applications such as defence and security, but also in critical applications such as autonomous cars and infrastructure.

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8 Conclusion

This document summarises the findings of the Platforms4CPS project, to develop a CPS Community Roadmap, a Technology and Research Radar and derive recommendations for strategic action required for the future evolution and deployment of CPS. Progress in different research and technological fields have a vast impact on CPS development and deployment. Amongst the **technological topics**, and related future research priorities integration and interoperability were of high importance in early roadmaps and remain important until today. The topic is connected to **digital platforms and reference architectures**, as well as the work on the right standards to help successful implementation of CPS. There is a very fragmented landscape of vertical and horizontal as well as open and closed platforms today. This is expected to move more and more towards composable, plug-and-play components, federated towards increasingly decentralised dynamic platform compositions. The digital platforms of the future are foreseen to become trusted multi-sided CPS market places within business ecosystems. **Autonomous systems** will evolve from self-healing, self-learning to self-reconfiguration and full-autonomous decision-making as well as from machine learning, pattern-recognition, and data-fusion towards algorithms to extract filtered information. Increasing integration of cobots and user interface adaptability will steer towards AI-enabled assistants. The human becoming part of the system will be a main future challenge to be solved by new **CPS engineering** approaches suitable for the ever-growing complexity in evolving systems. Moreover, managing composability with systems of agile and intelligent CPS devices in highly-dynamic environments and uncertain contexts are needed. **CPS safety, security**, trustworthiness, compliance and transparency are main priorities in relation to CPS deployment and have to be implemented by design and co-engineered. Frameworks for legislation, certification, and cybersecurity are needed. Ensuring trust and considering ethics is of utmost importance as well as **maintaining sovereignty** in key value chains.

Innovation accelerators, needed for successful implementation are multi-disciplinarity and **cross-fertilising** approaches as well as coordinated collaboration to **reduce fragmentation** across the EU. T-shape education, lifelong learning and **reskilling** and CPS enabled **business models** and services are very important. Demonstrators and **living lab** are essential to alleviate concerns and regulatory, legal and ethical issues to ensure a reliable framework. Not only societal dialogue and awareness raising but real **user acceptance** and trust are seen as crucial elements of future CPS success. Further points included to focus EC incentives on **open approaches** such as open data, open platform building, open innovations as well as open source solutions.

In the shorter term, the priorities above begin to be addressed under Horizon 2020 and existing Digitising European Industry activities via engagement with and expansion of the Digital Innovation Hubs, linking PPPs to work in synergy and supporting the development of platforms and large-scale pilots in key domains such. For the longer term, Platforms4CPS has identified a number of key emerging themes, including the need to master 'trustworthy CPS for AI-enabled autonomous systems with humans in the loop', exploit 'CPS edge computing' and 'co-engineering of CPS system attributes' and provide 'trust' as well as 'maintaining sovereignty' in key value chains. It has to be emphasised, that the research priorities and technological developments have to be embedded into a suitable innovation environment answering real societal needs. The 'mission based approach' of Horizon Europe is expected to be linking the research priorities with the grand challenges faced by humanity, providing a more interactive approach with society and a positive vision, steering future research and innovation.

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Picture: Platforms4CPS Consortium Meeting in Karlsruhe on the 22nd of August 2017

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